

CAIRT-PerReC

CAIRT Phase A Mission Performance and
Requirement Consolidation (PerReC)
Activity

ESA/ESTEC contract 4000136480/21/NL/LF CCN1

Deliverable D-09-07

CAIRT measurement requirements assessment

**Technical note on horizontal vs. vertical atmospheric
variability**

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Reference Number: DEL-09-07-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-1.0

Status: Final

Version/revision: 1.0

Date: 16.08.2024

<i>ESA Study Contract Report</i>		
<i>ESA Contract</i> 4000136480/21/N L/LF CCN1	<i>D09-07- Horizontal vs. vertical atmospheric variability</i>	<i>Contractor</i> Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
<p>In this document the global variability of different atmospheric parameters (pressure, temperature, water vapour and ozone mixing ratios) is visualized to compare the horizontal with the vertical absolute rates of change (per unit length, here per km) of these parameters.</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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DOCUMENT INFO

Reviewer

Reviewer	Organisation Short Name	E-Mail
All WP-Leader		

Document Control

Document version #	Date	Changes Made/Comments
V1.0	16-Aug-2024	First and final version

Signature by issuing authority and/or lead author

Table of Content

List of Figures.....	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Method.....	5
3. Results	5

List of Figures

Figure 1 Pressure gradients for 20060126.	7
Figure 2 Pressure gradients for 20100915.	8
Figure 3 Temperature gradients for 20060126.....	9
Figure 4 Temperature gradients for 20190915.....	10
Figure 5 Ozone volume mixing ratio gradients for 20060126.....	11
Figure 6 Ozone volume mixing ratio gradients for 20190915.....	12
Figure 7 Water vapour mass-mixing ratio gradients for 20190915.	13
Figure 8 Ratio of pressure gradients between different directions for 20060126 (dotted line indicates 50).14	
Figure 9 Ratio of pressure gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).15	
Figure 10 Ratio of temperature gradients between different directions for 20060126 (dotted line indicates 50).....	16
Figure 11 Ratio of temperature gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).....	17
Figure 12 Ratio of ozone volume mixing gradients between different directions for 20060126 (dotted line indicates 50).	18
Figure 13 Ratio of ozone volume mixing gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).	19
Figure 14 Ratio of water vapour mass-mixing gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).	20

1. Introduction

In this document the global variability of different atmospheric parameters (pressure, temperature, water vapour and ozone mixing ratios) is visualized to compare the horizontal with the vertical absolute rates of change (per unit length, here per km) of these parameters.

2. Method

We have used two exemplary global fields of pressure, temperature, ozone mixing ratio and water vapour specific humidity from ECMWF provided through FZJ (cairt.20060126T18.ml.fc.nc, 20190915T00.00.00.an.ml.nc). These datasets have a horizontal sampling of 0.1 deg and a vertically absolute altitude sampling of 0.5 km which is in the order of their inherent resolution (tbc).

The processing of the dataset has been performed as following:

- Gradients with respect to the absolute length scale [xxx/km] have been determined in west-east, south-north and in vertical bottom-top direction at each model grid point (lon,lat,z)
- For each altitude and latitude, the mean, the standard deviations around that mean and the 95% percentile of the *absolute* values of these gradients are determined around the latitude circles (i.e. over all longitudes).

3. Results

Figure 1-Figure 7 illustrate the obtained datasets for the different variables and dates. In each Figure:

- The 1st column shows the bottom-top ('up') gradients, the 2nd the south-north ('SN') and the 3rd, the west-east ('WE') ones.
- The rows show a different altitude range (each 4 km wide). In these ranges, the values of the mean of the absolute gradient values (blue), the standard deviation around the mean (orange), and 95%percentile averaged over the respective altitudes are displayed.

More adequate for the following discussion are Figure 8-Figure 12 which illustrate ratios of the gradients between different directions. In each Figure:

- The three columns depict the (latitude-dependent) ratios of the gradient SN/up, WE/up, and WE/SN
- As in the first set of Figures the rows contain the different altitude regions.

Main conclusion (see Figure 8-Figure 12) are (mind to look mainly at the blue and green curves, since the orange one is the std of the mean):

- Pressure (Figure 8, Figure 9):
 - Gradients in WE are generally smaller than in SN with a few exceptions. However, the factors do not often exceed a value of 2.
 - Gradients in vertical direction are about some 1000 up to 40000 times larger than horizontal ones.
- Temperature (Figure 10, Figure 11):
 - Gradients in both horizontal directions are very similar.
 - Gradients in vertical direction are about 50 up to 1000-2000 times larger than in the horizontal.
- Ozone volume mixing ratios (Figure 12, Figure 13):

- In general, mainly in the stratosphere the gradients are larger in SN than in WE direction (factor 1.5-2)
- Vertical gradients are in the troposphere by about 50-500 and in the stratosphere from 50 up to 500-1000 times larger than horizontal ones.
- Water vapour mass-mixing ratios (Figure 14):
 - Generally larger in SN than WE direction (factor 1.5 in troposphere, 2-5 in stratosphere)
 - Vertical gradients by about factors of 50-300 larger than horizontal ones in the troposphere and 50 up to 500-1000 in the stratosphere.

20060126T18, PRESS: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 1 Pressure gradients for 20060126.

20190915T00, PRESS: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 2 Pressure gradients for 20100915.

20060126T18, TEMP: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 3 Temperature gradients for 20060126.

20190915T00, TEMP: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 4 Temperature gradients for 20190915.

20060126T18, O3: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 5 Ozone volume mixing ratio gradients for 20060126.

20190915T00, O3: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 6 Ozone volume mixing ratio gradients for 20190915.

20190915T00, Q: mean, std and 95% percentile (along longitude circles)
of absolute values of gradients

Figure 7 Water vapour mass-mixing ratio gradients for 20190915.

20060126T18, PRESS: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 8 Ratio of pressure gradients between different directions for 20060126 (dotted line indicates 50).

20190915T00, PRESS: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 9 Ratio of pressure gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).

20060126T18, TEMP: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 10 Ratio of temperature gradients between different directions for 20060126 (dotted line indicates 50).

20190915T00, TEMP: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 11 Ratio of temperature gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).

20060126T18, O3: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 12 Ratio of ozone volume mixing gradients between different directions for 20060126 (dotted line indicates 50).

20190915T00, O3: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 13 Ratio of ozone volume mixing gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).

20190915T00, Q: ratio between different directions of mean and 95% percentile (along longitude circles) of absolute values of gradients

Figure 14 Ratio of water vapour mass-mixing gradients between different directions for 20190915 (dotted line indicates 50).